

Ring transformation reactions of 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl] sydrones; synthesis of oxime, hydrazone and dibromo derivatives of 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl] sydrones and 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]oxadiazolin-2-ones

Prashant R. Latthe^a, Ravindra R. Kamble^b and Bharati V. Badami^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Karnatak University, Dharwad-580 003, India

E-mail : bbadami@rediffmail.com

^bYuvaraja's College, University of Mysore, Mysore-570 005, India

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The oximes (3 and 4) and hydrazone (5a,b and 6a,b) derivatives of *m/p*-acetylphenylsydrones (1 and 2) have been subjected to one-pot ring conversion to the 3-[*m/p*-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]oxadiazolin-2-ones (7, 8, 9a,b and 10a,b). The α,β -unsaturated ketones (11a-h and 12a-h) obtained by the Claisen-Schmidt reaction, when subjected to ring conversion by bromine and acetic anhydride yielded the 3-[3/4-(3''-phenyl)-2'',3''-dibromo-1''-oxo propane-1''-yl]phenyl-5-methyl-2-oxo-1,3,4-oxadiazolinones (13a-h and 14a-h). Some of these compounds exhibited antimicrobial activity greater than the reference drug.

The synthesis and biological properties of 3-arylsydrones incorporated with wide variety of potent molecules have been reported from our laboratory earlier¹⁻⁵. During the present work we have utilised sydrones as synthons for heterocyclic synthesis as they readily undergo ring transformation to various heterocycles by 1,3-dipolar cycloadditions⁶. One such reaction has been reported from our laboratory⁷ wherein 3-arylsydrones have been converted to the corresponding 1,3,4-oxadiazolinones, by a simple one-pot reaction (85% yield). The ease of formation of these compounds from sydrones increases the synthetic utility of this ring conversion. Only few such oxadiazolinones obtained by difficulty and in very low yield, starting from phenylhydrazines have been cited in the literature⁸. In view of the fact that sydrone ring serves as a versatile synthon for such compounds, which are difficultly obtained by other methods, we thought of preparing some other substituted 1,3,4-oxadiazolinones. In the present work, we have extended this synthetic work to *m/p*-acetylphenylsydrones and its α,β -unsaturated ketone derivatives. We have carried out the conversion of the sydrones to the corresponding oxadiazolinones and also utilised the acetyl and enone residues for reactions to obtain the oximes, hydrazones and dibromoderivatives.

Results and discussion

The *m/p*-acetylphenylsydrones (1 and 2) were converted into oximes (3 and 4) and hydrazones (5a,b and 6a,b) derivatives of sydrones, which were then subjected to one pot-ring conversion to give corresponding oximes and

hydrazones of 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]oxadiazolin-2-ones (7, 8, 9a,b and 10a,b) (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

In another part of the work, the *m/p*-acetylphenylsydnones (1 and 2) were subjected to Claisen-Schmidt reaction. *m/p*-Acetylphenylsydnones (1 and 2) were condensed with aromatic aldehydes to get corresponding *m/p*-cinnamoylphenylsydnones (11a-h and 12a-h) (12a-h compounds have been reported by our earlier workers⁹), which on treatment with bromine in acetic anhydride underwent ring transformation reaction to give 1,3,4-oxadiazolinones accompanied by bromination of the unsaturated group to give 3-[3/4'-(3''-phenyl)-2'',3''-dibromo-1''-oxopropane-1''-yl]phenyl-5-methyl-2-oxo-1,3,4-oxadiazolinones (13a-g and 14a-g). The probable mechanism for sydnone ring conversion has been explained⁶ as follows (Scheme 2). However, with activating groups on the phenyl ring A, in particular the 3,4-dimethoxy derivatives (11h and 12h), bromination took place on the aromatic ring also. Interestingly, bromine entered *ortho* position of only one methoxy group to give the (3''-(3-bromo-4,5-dimethoxyphenyl) derivative (13h and 14h) while the *ortho* position of the other methoxy group would be sterically hindered for the attack of bromine. This reaction is unique that both addition and substitution of bromine takes place simultaneously.

Scheme 2

All the newly synthesized compounds were evaluated for their antibacterial activity against Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive *Bacillus cirroflagellous* bacteria and the antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium poa*, with Ciprofloxacin and Griseofulvin as reference drugs respectively. The compounds and the reference drugs were screened under identical conditions at a dose of 100 µg/1ml with DMF as the control solvent. Compounds 4, 8a and 6b in which sydnone ring is present at *p*-position to *N*-acetoxy oxime and hydrazone have shown antibacterial activity one and half times more than refer-

ence drug against *Escherichia coli* only. Whereas compounds 11d, 11e, 13d, 13e, 14d and 14e, with chloro and nitro groups as substituents have shown antibacterial activity more than that of reference drug against *Bacillus cirroflagellous*. Rest of the compounds have shown moderate activity against both microbes. Oxime of *p*-acetylphenylsydnone i.e. compound 4 exhibited one and half times more fungal growth inhibition against both fungal cultures whereas, compounds 11d, 11e, 13d, 13e and 14d possessed inhibitory action equal to reference drug against *Aspergillus niger* only. Rest of the compounds have shown moderate antifungal activity against both strains. In general the *p*-isomers of all these compounds have exhibited higher activity than *m*-isomers.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Nicolet-Impact 410 FT-IR spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. ¹H NMR and ¹³C spectra were recorded on Bruker-Varian 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer in CDCl₃ using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked by TLC on silica gel plate.

The *p*-acetylphenylsydnone (2) and corresponding chalcones (12a-h) were synthesized as reported earlier from this laboratory⁹. The corresponding *m*-isomers (1) and (11a-h) have been prepared by the same procedures. (1) (90%), m.p. 173–174° (Found : C, 58.80; H, 3.91; N, 13.70). C₁₀H₈N₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 58.82; H, 3.92; N, 13.72%; ν_{max} 1723 (sydnone C=O), 3100 cm⁻¹ (sydnone CH); δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, CH₃ acetyl), 6.7 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.1–7.4 (4H, m, ArH); 11a (71%), m.p. 198–199° (Found : C, 69.80; H, 4.08; N, 9.42). C₁₇H₁₂N₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 69.90; H, 4.10; N, 9.58%; ν_{max} 1739 (sydnone C=O), 1660 (ketone C=O), 3100 cm⁻¹ (sydnone CH); δ (CDCl₃) 6.9 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.1–7.4 (5H, m, ArH), 7.6–7.8 (3H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic); 11b (76%), m.p. 218–219° (Found : C, 70.54; H, 4.52; N, 9.13). C₁₈H₁₄N₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 70.59; H, 4.57; N, 9.15%; ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1739 (sydnone C=O), 1660 cm⁻¹ (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.12 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.2 (8H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic); 11c (79%), m.p. 180–181° (Found : C, 67.03; H, 4.32; N, 8.61). C₁₈H₁₄N₂O₄ calcd. for : C, 67.08; H, 4.30; N, 8.69%; ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1735 (sydnone C=O), 1666 cm⁻¹ (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 3.72 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.2 (8H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.6 (1H, d, vinylic); 11d (84%), m.p. 189–190° (Found : C, 62.41; H, 3.29; N, 8.49). C₁₇H₁₁ClN₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 62.48; H, 3.36; N, 8.58%; ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1739 (sydnone

C=O), 1660 cm^{-1} (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 6.95 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.2 (8H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic); **11e** (61%) m.p. 216–217° (Found : C, 60.49; H, 3.18; N, 12.39. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 60.53; H, 3.26; N, 12.46%); ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1731 (sydnone C=O), 1649 cm^{-1} (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.6 (1H, d, vinylic); **11f** (71%), m.p. 215–216° (Found : C, 62.41; H, 3.30; N, 8.54. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 62.48; H, 3.36; N, 8.58%); ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1731 (sydnone C=O), 1649 cm^{-1} (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.6 (1H, d, vinylic); **11g** (80%), m.p. 200–201° (Found : C, 62.40; H, 3.31; N, 8.51. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 62.48; H, 3.36; N, 8.58%); ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1731 (sydnone C=O), 1649 cm^{-1} (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.6 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic); **11h** (90%), m.p. 242–243° (Found : C, 64.70; H, 4.51; N, 7.89. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$ calcd. for : C, 62.48; H, 3.36; N, 8.58%); ν_{max} 3100 (sydnone CH), 1737 (sydnone C=O), 1678 cm^{-1} (ketone C=O); δ (CDCl_3) 3.8 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH_3), 7.2 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.3–8.4 (8H, m, ArH), 8.6 (1H, d, vinylic), 8.4 (1H, d, vinylic).

Preparation of oximes of 3-(3/4-acetylphenyl) sydnones (3 and 4) : To a solution of 3-(3/4-acetylphenyl) sydnones (**1** and **2**) (0.005 M) in ethanol (10 ml), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.0 g, 0.015 M) and pyridine (5 ml) were added and refluxed for 2 h on a steam-bath. The residue obtained after removal of solvent was crystallised from methanol to get yellow crystals. **3** (69%), m.p. 198–199° (Found : C, 54.76; H, 4.07; N, 19.12. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 54.79; H, 4.10; N, 19.17%); ν_{max} 3400 (oxime OH), 1723 (sydnone C=O), 3100 cm^{-1} (sydnone CH); δ (CDCl_3) 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3 of oxime), 4.0 (1H, s, oxime OH, D_2O exchanged), 6.7 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.1–7.4 (4H, m, ArH); **4** (72%), m.p. 152–153° (Found : C, 54.73; H, 4.04; N, 19.17. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_9\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 54.79; H, 4.10; N, 19.17%); ν_{max} 3430 (oxime OH), 1723 (sydnone C=O), 3100 cm^{-1} (sydnone CH); δ (CDCl_3) 2.5 (3H, s, CH_3 of oxime), 4.5 (1H, s, oxime OH, D_2O exchanged), 6.8 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.0–7.31 (4H, m, ArH).

Preparation of oximes of 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-ones (7 and 8). *General procedure* : To a solution of compounds (**3** and **4**) (0.005 M) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) at 0° was added bromine (0.3 ml) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) with constant stirring. After complete addition of bromine for 30 min, the reaction mixture was then heated at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into ice. The solid separated was filtered and

recrystallised from methanol to get oximes of 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-ones (**7** and **8**) in the form of white crystals. **7** (78%), m.p. 184–185° (Found : C, 50.16; H, 5.41; N, 17.53. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 50.20; H, 5.48; N, 17.57%); ν_{max} 1784 (lactone C=O), 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O of OCOCH_3); δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 2.2 (3H, s, C-5 CH_3), 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3 of oxime), 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3 of OCOCH_3), 7.82–7.93 (4H, m, ArH); **8** (63%), m.p. 172–173° (Found : C, 50.18; H, 5.40; N, 17.55. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$ calcd. for : C, 50.20; H, 5.48; N, 17.57%); ν_{max} 1766 (lactone C=O), 1742 cm^{-1} (C=O of OCOCH_3); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 2.39 (3H, s, CH_3 of oxime), 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3 of OCOCH_3), 6.9–7.01 (2H, d, ArH), 7.11–7.23 (2H, d, ArH); δ_{C} 12.2 (CH_3 oxadiazole), 12.6 (CH_3), 135 (q, Ar-C), 136 (q, Ar-N), 151.4 (q, C=N), 155.3 (q, C=O), 152.9 (q, ring C- CH_3), 118.2 and 127.3 (2C each Ar).

Preparation of hydrazones of 3-(3/4-acetylphenyl) sydnones (5a,b and 6a,b) and 3-[3/4-acetylphenyl]-5-methyl-[1,3,4]-oxadiazolin-2-ones (9a,b and 10a,b) : To a solution of 3-(3/4-acetylphenyl) sydnones (**1** and **2**) (0.005 M) in ethanol (20 ml), was added hydrazine hydrate (0.01M) in acetic acid (2 ml) and stirred at room temp. for 3 h. The solid separated was filtered and crystallised from methanol to get hydrazones (**5a,b** and **6a,b**) as bright yellow compounds. These hydrazones were converted to oxadiazolinones (**9a,b** and **10a,b**) by above mentioned general procedure using bromine and acetic anhydride. **5a** (72%), m.p. 152–153° (Found : C, 55.02; H, 4.55; N, 25.66. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 55.04; H, 4.58; N, 25.68%); ν_{max} 3440, 3350 (NH_2), 1725 (sydnone C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3 of hydrazone), 4.58 (2H, s, NH_2 , D_2O exchanged), 6.6 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.11–7.40 (4H, m, ArH); **5b** (74%), m.p. 164–165° (Found : C, 65.28; H, 4.74; N, 19.02. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 65.38; H, 4.76; N, 19.04%); ν_{max} 3480 (NH), 1715 (sydnone C=O), 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 2.45 (3H, s, CH_3 of hydrazone), 4.6 (1H, s, C=NNH, D_2O exchanged), 6.5 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.13–7.55 (9H, m, ArH); **6a** (68%), m.p. 158–160° (Found : C, 55.01; H, 4.43; N, 25.67. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 55.04; H, 4.58; N, 25.68%); ν_{max} 3495, 3360 (NH_2), 1705 (sydnone C=O), 1625 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl_3) 2.41 (3H, s, CH_3 of hydrazone), 4.28 (2H, s, NH_2 , D_2O exchanged), 6.5 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.25–7.31 (2H, d, ArH), 7.31–7.37 (2H, d, ArH); **6b** (76%), m.p. 205–206° (Found : C, 65.26; H, 4.72; N, 19.00. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 65.38; H, 4.76; N, 19.04%); ν_{max} 3502 (NH), 1710 (sydnone C=O), 1625 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ_{H} ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 2.40 (3H, s, CH_3 of PhNH), 5.43 (1H, s, C=NNH, D_2O exchanged), 6.9 (1H, s, sydnone CH), 7.15–7.55 (9H, m, ArH); δ_{C} ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 13.3 (CH_3), 95.4 (sydnone CH), 138.5 (C=N), 169.3

(sydnone C=O), 135.6 (q, Ar-C), 142.3 (q, Ar-NH), 146.2 (q, Ar-sydnone), 113.9, 118, 120.1, 120.4 and 130.5 (1C each of Ar-NH), 129.1 and 129.5 (2C of Ar-sydnone); **9a** (65%), m.p. 204–205° (Found : C, 54.91; H, 5.24; N, 21.30). $C_{12}H_{14}N_4O_3$ calcd. for : C, 54.96; H, 5.34; N, 21.37%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3425 (NH), 1776 (lactone C=O), 1662 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.31 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃ of hydrazone), 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃ of amide), 6.01 (1H, s, NH of hydrazone, D₂O exchanged), 7.21–7.52 (4H, m, ArH); **9b** (70%), m.p. 195–196° (Found : C, 63.85; H, 5.26; N, 16.51). $C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_3$ calcd. for : C, 63.90; H, 5.32; N, 16.56%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1788 (lactone C=O), 1654 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.24 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃ of phenyl hydrazone), 2.41 (3H, s, CH₃ of amide), 7.14–7.67 (9H, m, ArH); **10a** (84%), m.p. 223–225° (Found : C, 54.91; H, 5.28; N, 21.27). $C_{12}H_{14}N_4O_3$ calcd. for : C, 54.96; H, 5.34; N, 21.37%; $\nu_{\max}$ 3425 (NH), 1773 (lactone C=O), 1653 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.26 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 2.31 (3H, s, CH₃ of hydrazone), 2.50 (3H, s, CH₃ of amide), 5.24 (1H, s, NH of hydrazone, D₂O exchanged), 7.34–7.45 (2H, d, ArH), 7.56–7.67 (2H, d, ArH); **10b** (61%), m.p. 143–144° (Found : C, 63.83; H, 5.28; N, 16.55). $C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_3$ calcd. for : C, 63.90; H, 5.32; N, 16.56%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1784 (lactone C=O), 1651 cm^{-1} (amide C=O); δ (CDCl₃) 2.14 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 2.18 (3H, s, CH₃ of phenylhydrazone), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃ of amide), 7.28–7.57 (9H, m, ArH).

Preparation of 3-[3'/4'-(3''-phenyl)-2'',3''-dibromo-1''-oxo propane-1''-yl] phenyl-5-methyl-2-oxo-1,3,4-oxadiazolinones (13a-h and 14a-h): These compounds were also prepared according to the general procedure mentioned as above using bromine and acetic anhydride. **13a** (91%), m.p. 183–185° (Found : C, 46.29; H, 2.92; N, 5.94). $C_{18}H_{14}Br_2N_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 46.38; H, 3.00; N, 6.01%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1777 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ketone C=O), 1604 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–8.2 (9H, m, ArH); **13b** (74%), m.p. 224–225° (Found : C, 47.72; H, 2.65; N, 5.80). $C_{19}H_{13}Br_2N_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 47.79; H, 2.72; N, 5.87%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1777 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ketone C=O), 1604 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃ phenyl), 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–8.2 (9H, m, ArH); **13c** (89%), m.p. 206–207° (Found : C, 46.58; H, 2.65; N, 5.64). $C_{19}H_{13}Br_2N_2O_4$ calcd. for : C, 46.62; H, 2.63; N, 5.67%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1770 (lactone C=O), 1685 (ketone C=O), 1604 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃ phenyl), 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 3.77 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–8.0 (9H, m, ArH); **13d** (71%), m.p. 211–212° (Found : C, 43.11; H, 2.54; N, 5.53). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1765 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ketone C=O), 1614 cm^{-1}

(C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–8.2 (9H, m, ArH); **13e** (60%), m.p. 229–230° (Found : C, 43.34; H, 2.63; N, 8.43). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2N_3O_5$ calcd. for : C, 46.62; H, 2.63; N, 5.67%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1770 (lactone C=O), 1683 (ketone C=O), 1609 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.35 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.54 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.75 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.25–8.45 (9H, m, ArH); **13f** (90%), m.p. 201–208° (Found : C, 43.05; H, 2.49; N, 5.51). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1757 (lactone C=O), 1685 (ketone C=O), 1609 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.76 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.84 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–7.99 (9H, m, ArH); **13g** (83%), m.p. 188–189° (Found : C, 43.12; H, 2.51; N, 5.54). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1775 (lactone C=O), 1687 (ketone C=O), 1608 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.38 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.53 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–8.01 (9H, m, ArH); **13h** (76%), m.p. 201–202° (Found : C, 45.60; H, 3.35; N, 5.25). $C_{20}H_{18}Br_2N_2O_5$ calcd. for : C, 45.63; H, 3.43; N, 5.32%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1777 (lactone C=O), 1690 (ketone C=O), 1613 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.88 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.2–7.62 (4H, m, ArH), 7.8 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.1 (1H, s, Ar-H); **14a** (81%), m.p. 189–190° (Found : C, 46.29; H, 2.98; N, 5.91). $C_{18}H_{14}Br_2N_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 46.38; H, 3.00; N, 6.01%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1775 (lactone C=O), 1680 (ketone C=O), 1607 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.6 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.22 (2H, d, ArH), 7.42 (2H, d, ArH), 7.45–7.63 (4H, m, ArH); **14b** (80%), m.p. 158–160° (Found : C, 47.70; H, 2.63; N, 5.80). $C_{19}H_{13}Br_2N_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 47.79; H, 2.72; N, 5.87%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1778 (lactone C=O), 1684 (ketone C=O), 1608 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.54 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.76 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.20 (2H, d, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, ArH), 7.45–7.63 (4H, m, ArH); **14c** (84%), m.p. 151–153° (Found : C, 46.57; H, 2.63; N, 5.64). $C_{19}H_{13}Br_2N_2O_4$ calcd. for : C, 46.62; H, 2.63; N, 5.67%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1768 (lactone C=O), 1684 (ketone C=O), 1618 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.56 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.81 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.23 (2H, d, ArH), 7.39 (2H, d, ArH), 7.43–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **14d** (75%), m.p. 161–162° (Found : C, 43.08; H, 2.50; N, 5.58). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1772 (lactone C=O), 1683 (ketone C=O), 1616 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.56 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.81 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.23 (2H, d, ArH), 7.39 (2H, d, ArH), 7.43–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **14e** (90%), m.p. 195–196° (Found : C, 43.44; H, 2.60; N, 8.39). $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2N_3O_5$ calcd. for : C, 46.62; H, 2.63; N, 5.67%; $\nu_{\max}$ 1772 (lactone C=O), 1680 (ketone C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 2.45 (3H, s, C-5 CH₃), 5.61 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.84 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.25

(2H, d, ArH), 7.39 (2H, d, ArH), 7.50–7.60 (4H, m, ArH); **14f** (78%), m.p. 193–194° (Found : C, 43.15; H, 2.53; N, 5.57. $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%); ν_{max} 1778 (lactone C=O), 1684 (ketone C=O), 1608 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH_3), 5.54 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.76 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.20 (2H, d, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, ArH), 7.45–7.63 (4H, m, ArH); **14g** (80%), m.p. 144–145° (Found : C, 43.11; H, 2.50; N, 5.51. $C_{18}H_{13}Br_2ClN_2O_3$ calcd. for : C, 43.15; H, 2.59; N, 5.59%); ν_{max} 1783 (lactone C=O), 1680 (ketone C=O), 1608 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.4 (3H, s, C-5 CH_3), 5.54 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.76 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.20 (2H, d, ArH), 7.38 (2H, d, ArH), 7.45–7.63 (4H, m, ArH); **14h** (61%), m.p. 208–209° (Found : C, 45.54; H, 3.41; N, 5.21. $C_{20}H_{18}Br_2N_2O_5$ calcd. for : C, 45.63; H, 3.43; N, 5.32%); ν_{max} 1775 (lactone C=O), 1675 (ketone C=O), 1613 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$) 2.41 (3H, s, C-5 CH_3), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.85 (3H, s, OCH_3), 5.56 (1H, d, C-2' H), 5.78 (1H, d, C-3' H), 7.21 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.62 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.8 (1H, s, Ar-H), 8.1 (1H, s, Ar-H).

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